

THE PROBLEM OF TEACHER-STUDENT INTERACTION IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Annotation: This article provides an analysis of the results of scientific research on the interaction between teachers and students in primary classes. In this, the scientific-research works aimed at studying the problem of teacher-student interaction in foreign psychology were discussed in detail. Also, the results of the correlation of the results of the determining and control experiments of the relationship between the teacher and the students were analyzed.

Key words: teachers, student, interaction, correlation coefficients, communicator, receiver in elementary grades.

The primary school period lasts from 6-7 to 9-10 years. One of the important mental characteristics of a 6-7-year-old child, which differs from children of other ages, is the presence of specific needs. In essence, these needs are not focused only on the acquisition of specific knowledge, skills, and abilities, but also reflect the desire to be a learner. Based on these needs, the child's desire to have his own portfolio, personal educational tools, a table for preparing lessons, a bookshelf, and to go to school every day like an adult. This need is of great importance in the formation of the child's personality, as well as in his socialization. The relationship between the teacher and the students is of particular importance.

When studying scientific researches in foreign psychology aimed at studying the problem of teacher-pupil interaction, most of them specifically note the need to take into account the specific psychological characteristics of the teacher-pupil relationship in the full-fledged formation of the student's personality.

In particular, according to the scientific analysis of R. Plomin and H. Hermans (1997), in fact, the perfect formation of a person is determined by the influence of three main factors: 1) Biological capabilities available in a person - this refers to the influence of the type of temperament on the processes of human interaction. 2) Creates a strategy of the process of subjective, that is, psychological possibilities of the person; he personally chooses to enter into mutual relations and fills and improves them in social life. 3) The process of interpersonal relations affects the social-cultural, spiritual-ethical formation of relations and the individual. Socio-cultural environment provides the formation of personality as the main mechanism for interpersonal relations. But all three factors affect each other in an integral relationship. Without this integrity, the complete development of the individual does not occur [5].

According to the research of A. Bandura (1997), in the process of interpersonal relations, the internal standard and the ability to self-control are revealed in a person based on the social-cognitive approach. As a result, in the process of cooperation, teachers, parents and peers should help the student activate his mental potential, form his personal standard, check his abilities and express himself [5].

Dj. According to Caprara et al.'s (1999) research analysis, adherence to prosocial behavior norms in relationships enables individuals to cooperate and help each other, i.e., creates mutual sympathy, combats depression and problem behavior that destroys the educational process. encourages. It is appropriate to help young people realize their intellectual potential in the process of interpersonal relations. This situation confirms that social and intellectual development is observed not only in this student, but also in his peers [5].

Bomrind, another foreign psychologist, has conducted a lot of research on the psychology of children. He says that parents often approach child education in three different ways. These are: respect - authority, authoritarian and liberal methods, which have a positive and sometimes negative effect on the child. . In his opinion, the 1st method, i.e. respect and reputation, gave the best results in raising a child. So, in the process of education, the teacher's respect and reputation also leads to a positive result, without a doubt.

In Scheler's research, people with their own "I" are described as people who can say "no". The period of saying "I", formed in the third year of life, is called the age of stubbornness. "I" does not appear in our mind, but it is directly experienced and assimilated. This acquisition and perception is deeper than "I" in our consciousness. It is directly related to our psyche and emotions. It exists even when we do not think about it, it does not disappear. Acceptance of "I" as a concrete reality appears in a child around the age of 10. It increases during pre-puberty. During this period, the child feels his personal "I" as a deep disaster, a tragedy separated from the outside world. Only when puberty is reached, the old "I" begins to be replaced by the new one. Perceived as "I am free and free" and "I am free-willed", the will in this urges me to strive for the manifestation of "I" [6].

The scientific researches of Russian psychologists who studied the psychological features of the relationship between the teacher and the student deserve special attention. Famous Russian scientists V.M. Bekhterev, B.G. Anan'ev, V.M. Myasishev, Yu.M. Zbrodin, A.N. Kharitonov, A.K. Belyaeva, G.M. Kuchinsky, V.B. Olshansky and others studied the mechanisms and laws of social cooperation related to human psychology, while another group of scientists studied the psychological aspects of teacher-student relationships during the educational process (L.S. Vygotsky, D.B. Elkonin, A.V. Petrovsky, A. A. Bodalev, V. Ya. Lyaudis, S. V. Kondratev, Ya. L. Kolominsky, I. Kon, N. F. Maslova, V. L. Levi and others).

According to the results of V.M. Bekhterev and V.M. Myasishev's research [3], personality is manifested as a product of mutual cooperation and relations with others, which describes the level of interest, excitement, desire or desire of the subjects of such cooperation and relations, and their behavior - appears in character, behavior, and experiences. A person's relationship is reflected in cooperation with different levels of activity, selectivity and positive or negative

aspects. Taking into account these factors ensures effective organization of cooperation activities.

A.V.Petrovsky stated that interpersonal relations should arise from team activities, organizing the teacher's effective relationship with students in the educational process is not only a means of satisfying their need for communication and interaction, but also an important means of mastering educational material [8].

D. B. Elkonin offers a different look at child and community cooperation. In his opinion, it is more correct to consider the system "Child and society" and not as "Child in society", and in this the child will not be opposed to society. According to him, the "Child-adult" system will become the "Child-adult community" system. The reason for this is the child himself, who is embodied as a person who does something useful for society. Adults perform a variety of tasks in work processes where they interact with others. Children learn the manners, types and tasks of adult interaction in their activities. D. B. Elkonin divides the activity of the child in the "Child - public subject" and "Child - senior public member" system, which is considered important in the growth and development of the child's personality in society, into two parts in historical processes. New forms of these relationships appear at school, and the "Child - adult" system takes on the following form [7]

B.G.Anan'ev, L.I.Bojovich, I.S.Slavitsa in their research evaluate that the "Child - teacher" system determines the relationship of the child with parents and children. According to them, this system becomes the center of the child's life, and the comforts and conditions of life depend on it.

A.A. Bodalev [4] has a different approach to this issue and believes that the relationship between the teacher and the student is a necessary basis for their effective cooperation. For this, teachers need to take into account the characteristics and qualities, goals and needs of students, and for the team to work moderately, the mental situation should be calm, friendly, sympathetic to each other. In order to create such a psychological environment in the team, the pedagogical skills of the teacher in the classroom and the leadership ability of the leaders in production are of great importance.

E. G'. Goz'iev (1994 - 2000) focuses on the issues of teaching young students to manage their own activities, consciously managing the moral and intellectual aspects of the child's personality during the educational process. In the process of education, the teacher, by exerting his influence on the student, inculcates personality qualities such as independence and awareness in him, in which self-management is manifested in the form of the "teacher-student" model, where the teacher is the "informer" and the student is the "receiver". showed that the student grows from external reception to independent organization of his activities. The learner learns to control after mastering the methods of a certain system. Therefore, it is important to teach young students self-control, which has a positive effect on the harmonious development of the individual. For this, the elementary school teacher should try to help plan educational activities, improve the qualities of will to think logically, manage interest in learning, organize the learning of working with books, lead team search activities, organize mutual support activities among students, and organize independent activities. specifically

notes that they may have the ability to consciously manage their personal, moral and mental activities [9].

G. Berdiev's (2000) scientific research work dedicated to the study of the specific characteristics of the dynamics of interpersonal relationship development in students with retarded mental development of primary grades analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively the role, status and dynamics of relationships of students of general education and auxiliary schools in mutual relations [2].

Methodology. At the end of the main phase of our experimental work on the research of primary school teacher-pupil relations, that is, at the end of our work on control experiments, we once again turned to the study of the level of relations between the teacher and the students. For this purpose, we focused on the statistical comparison of the results of the diagnostic and control experiments, using Yu. Ya. Rijonkin's "Methodology for studying the communicative interval".

Experimental work. The results of the diagnostic, i.e., experimental test of our research were characterized by the fact that in the system of relations between the teacher and the student, the teacher is the subject of communication, and the student in individual cases is embodied only in the position of receiving information, and children who have a complex that it is difficult to reveal their potential in communication.

Correlation of the results of students' relationship with teachers once again confirmed that positive changes were achieved in these relationships (Table 1). Among the correlation coefficients, it was witnessed that in the results of the students' communicativeness, receptivity, the communicative zone in the group, the teachers created a correct positive connection on these scales: the increase in the communicativeness of the students ($r=0.486$; $p<0.05$) leads to an increase in trust and goodwill in the relationship with their teachers. In addition to that, they also show that they are able to get the answers they expect from their teachers. In turn, it was noted that as a recipient, they can achieve a sincere and reliable relationship with their teachers and show themselves as partners ($r=0.610$; $p<0.01$).

1. – table. Correlation of the results of descriptive and control experiments of teacher-student relationship

		Teachers			
Teachers		Communication torus - L _k	Recipient - L _p	Guruhdagi communicativ e zone	Change in the communicative zone in the group
	Communicator -L _k	0,486**	0,513**	0,372*	0,172
	Recipient - L _p	0,610**	0,815**	0,108	0,220
	Guruhdagi communicative zone	0,412*	0,395*	0,805**	0,217
	Change in the communicative zone in the group	0,175	0,060	0,105	0,243

Note: * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$.

At the same time, we witnessed that students as recipients listen carefully to their teachers and allow their teachers to address them in the same way ($r=0.815$; $p < 0.05$). This indicates the attitude of the teacher at the level of recognition of students as individuals, listening to their experiences and problems.

It is embodied as one of the main methods of communication between the pedagogue and his students. It can be seen that students are able to form internal control during their relationship with their teachers. Because the formation of their self-confidence, the ability to overcome previous defects in their behavior determines their maturity as a person.

The development of internality in students forms the perception that they have a lot to do with solving life and interpersonal problems. With this, we can witness that our psychological correction works can bring changes in the students' behavior rather than their cognitive activity. If the status of externality was preserved in them, students would not be able to get rid of the effect of "flange effect" under the influence of a teacher or someone else's reprimand against their naturally existing sense of confidence even in normal relational conditions.

Conclusions and recommendations.

1. The teacher should not treat the student as a young child, but should take into account his feelings and experiences and allow him to express himself. Children's mental stress can persist for a long time as a result of a negative attitude during the preschool period or the first days of elementary school. This is the "first effect" and the child's attitude towards the teacher is preserved due to this impression.

2. Children who are unable to express themselves in communication with students, who have an empty psychological formation and nervous system, are separated from the group and tend to be lonely. It is necessary to study their individual-psychological characteristics, use incentives and support them in order to ensure their engagement.
3. Since the teacher's work requires excessive mental stress, he should refrain from anger, affect and outbursts in his relationship with students. Such situations immediately have a negative effect on the psyche of children with a complex.
4. Individual interaction between the teacher and the student is one of the important components of the pedagogue's professional activity. In the process of dealing with children, taking into account their psychology leads to the improvement of the teacher's attitude and work style.
5. Since the pedagogical activity is rich in various situations of complex relationship, the teacher should know the psychological characteristics of working with elementary school students and make it a habit to use the psychologist's advice about the school of pedagogical skills appropriately and systematically.

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